

USING OF METAPHOR OF WOUND IN KADZUO ISIGURO'S NOVELS

Ирсалиева Мадина Анварбек қизи

Ўзбекистон Миллий Университети

Хорижий филология факультети Факультетлараро

инглиз тили кафедраси ўқитувчиси

E-mail: irsalieva92@bk.ru

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ABSTRACT

It is known that the means of artistic language are widely used in works of art. The means of artistic language serve to reveal the purpose for which the writer is expressing. Kazuo Isiguro is one of the most influential writers in the world, especially in modern English literature. In 2017, he won the Nobel Prize for his novels. His work is multifaceted. Today, the author is a writer who reveals aspects of the Japanese and English nation. The different interpretations of the metaphor analyzed in Kazuo Isiguro's novels are revealed in the example of the fate of the novel's protagonists.

Kazuo Isiguro, one of the modern English writers, entered literature with his brilliant works. Kazuo Isiguro, who is of Japanese origin, tried to describe some of the features that are unique to the Japanese in his works. He is still one of the most versatile artists. There is no doubt that some researches are being conducted on the author's work. We see that Kazuo Isiguro has extensively interpreted the metaphor of injury in a number of novels. The author himself points out that there are injuries that lead to the creation of exactly the best novels. According to the writer, there is no way to cure or get rid of a heartbreaking wound. In 1995, the author's novel "The Unconsoled" was published. The novel begins with the theme of injury and pain. The writer describes the injury as follows: "Do you know how to dry out your pain, are you talking about heartache, No, no about injury. It's been a

year for him and he hasn't left me alone. Terrible injury. Mr. Brodsky, you mean heartache, Heartache is nothing. I was talking about a real injury"¹. The novel narrator himself recalls his exact injury and states that he did not get rid of it despite the fact that it had been him for many years. In general, the heroes of Kazuo Isiguro are people who have forgotten happy memories. They were affected differently by the injury. They were orphaned due to the injuries inflicted on them. Heroes who have experienced orphanhood will not forget this wound. One of the protagonists of Pale View of the Hills, Etsuko Nagasaki was separated from her parents by a bomb, Sashiko became an orphan, and Kaiko and Niki lost their homes. The wounds inflicted on them by this bomb will neither disappear nor be

¹ Kazuo I. The Unconsoled. L.:Faber and Faber 1995. – 3 p.

forgotten. Kazuo Ishiguro's 2000 novel, *When We Were Orphans*, reveals the heartache of the orphaned Banks, Sarah, and Jennifer. Pianist Ryder, the protagonist of *The Unconsolable*, would be touring in many countries and cities. Each time she attended a concert in a new location, she would look into the hall to see her parents. The metaphor, which is a means of artistic language mentioned above, is widely interpreted in the writer's work. In the literary dictionary, metaphor is one of the most common types of semantic migration and is interpreted as one of the types of migration based on similarity between objects and events². In this case, the metaphor is a hidden analogy, in which the thing being imitated, that is, the word that expresses it. The injury expressed by Kazuo Ishiguro signifies an unforgettable pain, not a physical one. The wound revealed by the novel's protagonists is extremely profound.

All the protagonists of the novel created by Kazuo Ishiguro have forgotten the happy past. The happy past has faded from memory due to the trauma inflicted on them. Now the wound in their souls is so ingrained that it is impossible to forget or forget. The narrator of *The Unconsolable* sees the remains of an old car in the ruins. The wreckage of the car suddenly reminds him of the happy moments of his childhood. In the back seat of the car, a toy awakens memories of his parents playing with the soldiers. As he recalls a moment of happy memories, Ryder feels that the trauma inflicted by happy memories hurts more. Ryder sits in the wreckage of an old car, trying to remember how that day ended. The author puts it this way: "As I

was sitting in the wreckage of the car, I tried to remember how the day ended. But all of a sudden, I remembered a fight in the house like a rainy storm and my father disappearing on the road"³. In recalling the memories he experienced, the writer emphasizes the events that left a scar rather than happy ones. This is also reflected in the novel *When We Were Orphans*. One of the novel's protagonists recalls his happy childhood moments when he and his mother played a chase on the lawn, unable to even remember who won at the end of the game. At the same time, she says she still remembers the injustice she felt at the time towards her mother.

Banks, on the other hand, comes to a house similar to the one in Shanghai where he spent his childhood. As he watches the house, he suddenly catches sight of the stairs. The stairs remind him of his childhood habits of sliding down the hill. It makes Banks smile for a moment, but he remembers being separated from his mother a few minutes later, and from that moment on, he never slipped down the stairs. Because of his separation from his mother, he even forgot about this hobby. The loss of his mother left a deep wound in his heart. In the author's series of novels, an unexpected detail, house, or item is reminiscent of the pain of an injury inflicted in the past. The writer himself also tries to vividly express whether the injury changes from day to day. The day the injury was initially inflicted is an attempt to forget it over the years, but each time the events reminiscent of the injury are revived and

² Куронов Д. Атабиётшунослик луғати. Тошкент: Академнашр. 2013. -170 б.

³ Kazuo I. *The Unconsolable*. L.: Faber and Faber 1995. – 275 p.

finally the wound is exhausted. Kazuo Isiguro expresses injury in his novels through types such as pain, horrible memories, anguish.

The writer tries to portray the wound in the protagonists through details such as a box, a box, or a box full of mysterious objects. Sashiko, the protagonist of the novel "Pale view of the Hills" puts Japanese love in a box on his way to America. It was one of the only memories of the service family Forty years later, the storyteller Etsuko mentions this box and service. It was the Japanese service that was a reminder of the lost family and the memories associated with it. As the box, expressed in detail, moves from novel to novel, the writer points out that it is associated not only with happy memories, but also with the box on the day the tragedy began. In *The Unconsoled*, Sophie loses a souvenir box and forgets about her father as a result. Saunders, on the other hand, tells the bitter story of being separated from the family as a result of an orange box exploding. Kazuo Isiguro continues to express the box not only as a simple item but also as a home symbol. In the novel *When We Were Orphans*, little Jennifer, who has become an orphan, is waiting for the day when she will receive a box of things. Jennifer, separated from home and family, tries to take the belongings in a box and take them with her. But the box does not arrive when you reach the destination. Receives a letter from the airline about the loss of a box containing personal belongings. This letter is an introduction to the memories of the whole house. For little Jennifer, the box was a big thing that reminded her of her home. This situation is repeated in the novel "Never let me Go". Little Mariko, depicted in the novel

Pale Pale of Hills, wins a lottery ticket for a big box that can do homework for kittens. Little Mariko was so eager to win a box that could only be a haven for kittens in the lottery game that it was as if this wish was the only wish in Mariko's life. The box for the kittens could be a real home, and in this house the kittens could grow up peacefully as Mariko said. Researcher Shaffer B, while studying the writer's work, pays close attention to the detail of the box, noting that Mariko served as a sign of losing the winning box he won for vegetables. According to the researcher, the boxes expressed by Kazuo Isiguro injure a person, and this pain is always remembered by the heroes⁴. Etsuko, the narrator of the novel *Pale Pale of Hills*, remembers her husband's father as she talks about her daughter who died. Forty years ago in Nagasaki, Etsuko's father-in-law, Ogata-san, also remembers practicing the violin, which he did to improve his relationship with his son. For Etsuko, Ogata-san is a esteemed man who played the violin at night to pay off debts and thereby try to improve the life of the family. Nevertheless, the life of this peaceful family was ruined by a bomb dropped on Nagasaki. As one of the saddest points of the novel, Kazuo Isiguro pays great attention to this.

Many researchers point out that Kazuo, who immigrated to England at a young age, was not indifferent to the horrific events that befell his nation as he grew up in British society. The abundance of such painful wounds in his novels is vividly illustrated in the example of the protagonists. B.Luis and M.Petru, who

⁴ Shaffer B. *Understanding Kazuo Isiguro*. Columbia: University of South Carolina Press, 1998. 141 p.

studied the work of Kazuo Isiguro, in the novel *The Unconsoled*. Hasrat, commented that the author Ryder could observe several groups of twin characters. According to them, Kazuo Isiguro is a writer who was not indifferent to the fate of the nation despite growing up in English society⁵. In addition to the images typical of the British, the writer skillfully depicts the heroes of the Japanese nation. He also uses Japanese names in their naming.

It is no coincidence that multiculturalism in a globalized English society allows the writer to create such images. The writer leaves the reader to find a solution to the question of which of them is more tragic, that the wound inflicted on the heart affects both the Japanese and the British.

D.O. Crider, who interviewed Kazuo Isiguro points out that from the time his heroes were injured in the past, we still see them in the background of that scene⁶. The writer himself emphasized that no matter how traumatic an injury is it can have a direct impact not only on the individual but also on the destiny of society. As the writer creates the destiny of each hero, he also reveals their uniqueness. There is an immortal scar on the fate of heroes connected at one point in life. The wound that binds them has a strong effect on them and reminds them to be unforgettable. An important aspect of Kazuo Isiguro is that he seems to be able to combine the English

and Japanese mentality. The main reason for this is that he received a British-style education while he was Japanese. In his novels, too, this strong influence is evident. He tries to rely on reality in describing the fate of Japanese heroes. He tries to reveal them as they are. In English heroes, however, English society was able to maintain the aristocratic character. This is especially noticeable in his novel *The Remains of the Day*. Novel hero Stevens will serve Lord Darlington all his life. His duty is also seen in this service. After the death of Lord Darlington, the English Lord retained this duty and devotion. For Stephen, it becomes his habit to bring breakfast or a drink to the lord on a platter every day. He serves the Lord faithfully. There is an unchangeable character in the nature of Stevens, who considers it his duty to serve the aristocracy. Among the novels of Kazuo Isiguro, the protagonist of this work is not repeated in other works. But the writer gradually reveals that there is a scar on his heart as well.

It can be observed that the metaphor of trauma is expressed differently in the novels of the English writer Kazuo Isiguro, analyzed above. The versatile artist himself turns the reader over to the question of whether the wound can be treated. We can see that in the radical twists that took place in the fate of the heroes, he tried to reveal the immortal traces of the wound in detail.

⁵ Lewis B. Kazuo Isiguro. Manchester and NY: Manchester University Press, 2000. 176 p.; Petry M. *Narratives of Memory and Identity: The Novels of Kazuo Isiguro*. Frankfurt: Peter Lang, 1999. 174 p.

⁶ Crider D.O. «Rooted in a Small Space»: An Interview with Kazuo Isiguro // *The Kenyon Review*. 1998. Vol. 20. P. 152.

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